

INFLUENCE OF EXTERNAL BARRIER STRUCTURES ON THERMAL PHYSICAL PROPERTIES.

Asatov Nurmuxammad Abdunazarovich
Tojimurodov Abdurahmon Abdurashidovich

“Construction of Buildings and Structures”

Jizzakh polytechnic institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6390345>

Abstract: The article analyzes the current state of the problems encountered in the design of buildings. To this end, various engineered discussed concept upon which the design of roofs formed. As one of the elements of the mechanism of implementation of these plans are specific examples of the construction of energy-efficient roof.

Key words: energy efficient, roof constructions, buildings

From the beginning of time, humans have used sunlight. The beginnings of architecture in Central Asia, especially in Uzbekistan, date back to the III century BC. Many of the buildings and structures that were built in the IXth Century and have survived to the present day are rightly considered to be the pinnacle of the art of construction. Buildings and structures built in Samarkand, Bukhara, Khorezm, Tashkent and other cities in the XVI-XVII centuries can be considered as a high school of construction. clearly visible. 90% of primary energy is lost in mining, production, transportation, storage and consumption of energy resources. This is primarily due to the fact that the raw material undergoes many technological processes before it reaches the consumer, and the traditional energy supply becomes more expensive. Therefore, architects and builders in the development of concepts for the development of architectural design of the XXI century, the city structure and individual buildings in working projects to preserve natural resources and as much as possible new solutions, especially solar energy. llash is required. New sources include solar energy, wind energy, hydropower, and deep-seated energy. The country's heat balance accounts for 90% of non-renewable energy sources, of which 30% is oil, 40% is gas and 20% is coal. All fossil fuels are a form of solar energy that has gone through various stages, regenerated and reached us millions of years later, and is in danger of running out and becoming more expensive. The energy of the light that the sun sends to the earth is really huge, 47% of the 100% of the energy coming to the earth falls to the earth, the rest of the energy is distributed to the universe and provides the planet's heat balance. Solar energy per square

meter of the Earth's surface is 160 W / m , but these figures vary for different latitudes. Humidity, cloudy weather, atmospheric dust, altitude, seasons, daily temperature and more. The current issue is how much of the world's solar energy is used for human consumption. This can be achieved by using different construction methods using new energy sources when building a new building or reconstructing an existing building. In the 60s and 70s, when the first steps were taken to use non-conventional forms of energy in the CIS countries, autonomous power-supply photovoltaics appeared and justified itself in space. By the end of the 1980s, solar panels were installed to provide hot water to an area of $150,000 \text{ m}^2$. The production of solar collectors amounted to 80 thousand m^2 per year. As a result of the economic difficulties of the 1990s, the development of non-conventional energy in our country has been halted. But today, the use of non-conventional energy sources is becoming more widespread around the world and in our country. In order to receive solar energy, the receiving surface must be on the south side, which means that the latitude of residential buildings is considered to be efficient. Passive use of solar radiation by receiving direct light from glass windows is used indirectly through walls, roofs, barriers of winter gardens.

The disadvantage of solar energy is that it is unique to all alternative energy sources. For example, solar radiation activity varies from 2.2 MWh / year depending on the latitude, and the daily oscillations can be considered even higher. Today, Uzbekistan has 3,800 boiler and 1,136 thermal power plants, thousands of kilometers of communication pipelines, which emit harmful substances, combustion products and require new investments. Uzbekistan is a republic with more than 300 sunny days a year. The total capacity of solar energy is estimated at 95 billion tons of conventional fuel, 1% of which is consumed by wind turbines, which is comparable to the consumption of energy in Uzbekistan as a whole.

In the design and construction of modern residential buildings and structures, first of all, the climatic characteristics of the construction site are taken into account.

As for the climate of Uzbekistan, it is located in the northern hemisphere, in the central part of Central Asia. In addition to its geographical location, the climate of Uzbekistan is influenced by the altitude and topography of its territory.

A quarter of the country's territory is mountainous, the rest is 100-200 m above sea level. The plain joins the hills from west to southeast and the hills to the mountains.

The territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is 447.4 thousand km² and borders more than 5300 km, mainly between the Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers. The area of plains (deserts) is 75% of the territory of the republic. The deserts are located at an altitude of 300-400 m above sea level, and the climate is sharply continental. The average temperature in July is 30°-32° C, and in January -2°-3° C. Annual precipitation is around 100-300 mm. The part of the territory of the republic at an altitude of 400-1200 meters above sea level is the Adir region.

The climate of the hills is more temperate than the desert. The rainfall is higher (300-450 mm) than in the desert, and the summer lasts longer.

The mountainous region is located at an altitude of 1000-2800 m above sea level. Summers in the mountains are short and cool, with lots of rain and long winters.

Strong winds blow in many parts of Uzbekistan, especially in the plains. According to the requirements of hygienists, builders and QMQ 2.01.01-97 *, QMQ 2.01.01-94, the size-historical and design solution of buildings under construction in each climate zone and their use in these climatic conditions should be different.

The design of buildings and their external barriers will focus primarily on creating a temperate climate for people to live and work. For humans to live, the average temperature should be 18-24° C. If the room temperature is below + 8 ° C, it is cold, +8 ° +15 ° is cool, +16° + 28° is warm, and above 28° C is hot. Heating buildings in winter and protecting them from solar radiation in summer depends on the climate of the region.

For example, the average July temperature in Tashkent is + 28.6° C and the maximum absolute temperature is +44.5° C, the minimum absolute temperature is -31.7° C, and the maximum daily amplitude of temperature fluctuations is +24.9° C. In Termez, these values are +30.4 ° C and 27.6 ° C. The coldest daily temperature for the winter in Samarkand is -18 ° C with an annual temperature of 0.98, in Nukus it is -27° C and in Jizzakh -22° C. However, in the future it is recommended to take these indicators as a result of practical research.

In very cold climates, the design of public and residential buildings does not include balconies, loggias and balconies. Residential buildings have the same height, and light lanterns are rarely used. For centuries, in glacial areas, the first

floor of a building was left open to allow wind to blow. Otherwise, the heat from the building will melt the ice and cause the building to collapse.

The duration of the hot climate in Tashkent is more than 5-6 months. Therefore, natural ventilation is used in the buildings to keep the room temperature from overheating. In addition, the walls and windows of buildings should be designed to protect from solar radiation (screens - blinds), and natural ventilation measures should be taken on the roofs of solid attics.

In sharply continental climates, natural ventilation of buildings using windows at night and closing windows during the day is effective in protecting them from high temperatures. In industrial buildings, where the production process is subject to certain requirements, artificial cooling, ie air conditioning, creates a temperate climate in the rooms.

Currently, many one- and two-storey industrial buildings are being built in villages and towns on the basis of standard designs.

The convenience of this is that if the upper part of the two-storey buildings is protected from solar radiation by the method of natural ventilation, the high temperature at the bottom will be absorbed into the ground.

One of the most effective ways to protect against solar radiation is to plant shady, cool trees around the industrial building.

In areas where strong winds and rainfall are observed, the outer surface of the structures is covered with a waterproof ceramic and moisture-proof layer. In areas with low rainfall, the walls of buildings are plastered with a 2-4 cm thick cement-sand mixture. It is known that the thermal conductivity and moderate humidity of external barrier structures depend on the climate and indoor environment. In order to create a temperate climate inside the rooms of the building and to choose the rational external barrier structures, their thermal-physical and humidity state engineering calculations are performed. We will look at the main climatic parameters used to design exterior barriers.

Использованная литература:

1. Sagatov B. U. About transfer of effort through cracks in ferro-concrete elements //European science review. – 2016. – №. 7-8. – С. 220-221.
2. Ablayeva U., Normatova N. Energy saving issues in the design of modern social buildings //Problems of Architecture and Construction. – 2019. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 59-62.
3. Норматова Н. А. Проектирование энергосберегающих зданий в условиях узбекистана //Academy. – 2020. – №. 11 (62).

4. Asatov N. A., Sagatov B. U., Maxmudov B. I. O. G. L. Tashqi to'siq konstruksiyalarini issiqlik fizik xususiyatlariga ta'siri //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 182-192.
5. Аблаева Ў. Ш., Норматова Н. А. Тошкент: лойиҳалашнинг анъанавийликдан hozirgi кунигача //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 206-216.
6. Аблаева Ў. Ш., Норматова Н. А. Ўзбекистондаги мавжуд биноларнинг энергия тежамкор шамоллатиладиган тизимлари асосий системалари //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 193-205.
7. Sagatov B. U. O'zbekistonda energiya tejamkor binolar qurilishining ahvoli //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 261-265.

